

Comparison of radiant intensity in aqueous media using experimental and numerical simulation techniques

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Supplementary Information

ZeMax Optic Studio Design Layout:

Object ID	Object Type	Comment	Ref Object	Inside Of	X Position	Y Position	Z Position	Tilt About X	Tilt About Y	Tilt About Z	Material
1	Null Object		0	0	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	-
2	Rectangular Volume	Package	0	0	-34.633	-0.900	-30.850	0.000	0.000	0.000	-
3	Array		0	0	-34.633	-0.900	-30.850	0.000	0.000	0.000	-
4	Null Object		0	0	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	-
5	Source Radial	LED	0	0	-34.633	-0.900	-30.420	0.000	0.000	0.000	-
6	Null Object		0	0	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	-
7	Rectangle	Long Reflector 1	0	0	0.000	3.381	-27.375	75.000	0.000	0.000	MIRR...
8	Rectangle	Long Reflector 2	0	0	0.000	-3.381 P	-27.375 P	-75.000	0.000	0.000	MIRR...
9	Null Object		0	0	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	-
10	Rectangle	Short Reflector 1	0	0	36.665	0.000	-27.284	0.000	-86.167	0.000	MIRR...
11	Rectangle	Short Reflector 2	0	0	-36.665 P	0.000	-27.284 P	0.000	86.167 P	0.000	MIRR...
12	Null Object		0	0	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	-
13	Rectangular Pipe	Mechanic 1	0	0	0.000	0.000	-30.850	0.000	0.000	0.000	MIRR...
14	Rectangular Pipe	Mechanic 2	0	0	0.000	0.000	-30.850	0.000	0.000	0.000	MIRR...
15	Null Object		0	0	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	-
16	Rectangular Volume	Glue Window	0	0	0.000	0.000	-22.300	0.000	0.000	0.000	QUAR...
17	Rectangular Volume	Removeable Window	0	0	0.000	0.000	-21.300	0.000	0.000	0.000	QUAR...
18	Null Object		0	0	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	-
19	Detector Rectangle		0	0	0.000	0.000	2.500	0.000	0.000	0.000	-
20	Detector Rectangle		0	0	0.000	0.000	4.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	-
21	Detector Rectangle		0	0	0.000	0.000	8.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	-
22	Detector Rectangle		0	0	0.000	0.000	14.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	-
23	Detector Rectangle		0	0	0.000	0.000	20.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	-
24	Detector Rectangle		0	0	0.000	0.000	24.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	-
25	Detector Rectangle		0	0	0.000	0.000	25.500	0.000	0.000	0.000	-

Figure S1. Screen grab of ZeMax optic studio.

Mesh Sensitivity Analysis on DOM:

Mesh sensitivity analysis was conducted for each of the wavelengths. Figure S2 – S4 show a plot of number of cells in mesh versus simulated peak intensity values. Optimum mesh used for simulations are seen in Table S1

Table S1. Optimum mesh data.

Wavelength	Optimum Element Size (m)	Number of cells	Number of nodes
265 nm	0.0007	416887	80103
275 nm	0.0007	419567	80611
310 nm	0.0007	417174	80135

Figure S2. Mesh sensitivity analysis for 265 nm source

Figure S3. Mesh sensitivity analysis for 275 nm source.

Figure S4. Mesh sensitivity analysis for 310 nm source

Rollover test:

Rollover test is conducted by light source manufacturers to conclude a safe working current and optical power output from the light source as operated by the device electronics and controlling system. The following figures outline the data from rollover tests conducted on the three wavelengths studied.

Figure S5. Rollover test data FX-1 (a) 265 nm, (b) 275 nm and (c) 310 nm.

Optical model vs experimental data (other wavelengths):

Figure S5. Optical model comparison between datasheet and actual power simulations (a) 275 nm, (b) 310 nm

ZeMax and radiometry (other wavelengths):

Figure S6. Plot of peak intensity vs working distance (a) 275 nm, (b) 310 nm

Table S2. Recorded peak intensity at multiple working distances using radiometry and ZeMax (without the effect of quartz tube)

Working Distance (mm)	Measured Peak Intensity (275 nm) (mW cm ⁻²)		Measured Peak Intensity (310 nm) (mW cm ⁻²)	
	Radiometry	ZeMax	Radiometry	ZeMax
14	26.486 ± 0.22	28.068	33.089 ± 1.2	36.486
19	20.180 ± 0.56	20.847	25.891 ± 0.21	27.224
24	16.209 ± 0.44	17.477	20.359 ± 0.34	21.706
29	14.277 ± 0.18	15.772	17.564 ± 0.22	17.690
34	12.623 ± 0.14	13.887	16.432 ± 0.16	14.978

Effect of quartz tube (other wavelengths):

Figure S7. Plot of peak intensity vs working distance in the presence of quartz tube (a) 275 nm, (b) 310 nm

Table S3. Recorded peak intensity at multiple working distances using radiometry and ZeMax for effect of quartz

Working Distance (mm)	Measured Peak Intensity (275 nm) (mW cm ⁻²)		Measured Peak Intensity (310 nm) (mW cm ⁻²)	
	Radiometry	ZeMax	Radiometry	ZeMax
14	23.856 ± 0.75	25.287	31.579 ± 0.26	33.473
19	17.718 ± 0.62	18.781	23.563 ± 0.24	24.976
24	14.854 ± 0.11	15.745	18.787 ± 0.12	19.914
29	13.405 ± 0.22	14.209	15.311 ± 0.37	16.229
34	11.803 ± 0.14	12.511	12.964 ± 0.12	13.741

Quartz tube transmission curve (FAB027469, GE214):

Figure S8. Fused quartz transmittance curve as obtained from the manufacturer (see white line for GE214 material type)

ZeMax vs DOM (other wavelengths):

Figure S9. Comparison between ZeMax, DOM and radiometry (a) 275 nm, (b) 310 nm

Table S4. Recorded peak intensity at multiple working distances using DOM and ZeMax (in air)

Working Distance (mm)	Measured Peak Intensity (275 nm) (mW cm ⁻²)		Measured Peak Intensity (310 nm) (mW cm ⁻²)	
	ZeMax	DOM	ZeMax	DOM
14	28.069	27.227	36.486	34.297
19	20.847	19.805	27.225	25.863
24	17.477	15.904	21.707	20.621
29	15.772	14.353	18.693	17.571
34	13.887	12.638	17.978	17.439

Data on ferrioxalate actinometry:

Incident Area – 0.004712389 cm²

Table S5. Actinometry data on incident irradiation

Wavelength (nm)	Incident Irradiation in E/s			Average Incidence Irradiation in E/s	Error
	1	2	3		
265	3.66*10 ⁻⁶	3.61*10 ⁻⁶	3.79*10 ⁻⁶	3.69*10 ⁻⁶	0.000005%
275	5.56*10 ⁻⁶	5.55*10 ⁻⁶	5.70*10 ⁻⁶	5.60*10 ⁻⁶	0.000005%
310	6.28*10 ⁻⁶	6.68*10 ⁻⁶	6.37*10 ⁻⁶	6.44*10 ⁻⁶	0.000012%
Wavelength (nm)	Incident Irradiation in W/m ²			Average Incidence Irradiation in W/m ²	Error
	1	2	3		
265	351.32	346.21	363.93	353.82	5.26
275	513.89	512.73	526.40	517.67	4.37
310	514.25	546.98	521.94	527.72	9.88

(a) 265 nm

(b) 275 nm

(c) 310 nm

Figure S10. Plots of E/L vs time for ferrioxalate actinometry (a)265 nm, (b) 275 nm, (c) 310 nm